

TOWARDS A COMPOSITE CIVIL AIRCRAFT WING

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SUMMARY: Following a visit to Germany by personnel representing the Australian Aerospace Industry in 1994 a research program was commenced mid-1995 by the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures. This program undertook the investigation of cost effective design/manufacture of commercial aircraft composite wing stringers and ribs in cooperation with Daimler-Benz Aerospace Airbus (DASA) and supported by the Ministry for Education, Research and Technology, BMBF, Bonn. This paper details the research and development undertaken to progress towards cost efficient manufacturing technologies for wing stringer (T-section) production and indicates the techniques used and the outcomes derived from the early stages of the program.

KEYWORDS: wing, stringers, resin transfer moulding, tooling, test

INTRODUCTION

Conventional pre-preg stringer designs from DASA were utilised as the baseline. The overall wing tasks undertaken by the CRC-AS included design, manufacture, development, test and sub-element qualification. The program was undertaken in two phases:

Phase 1 investigated various manufacturing techniques and material types which could be used in stringer design. However, as the prime deliverables to DASA were 2 metre stringers for use on a compression test panel in a short timescale, qualified unidirectional and standard 5H satin fabrics were utilised for initial design work. These stringers represented the type 2, or intermediate stringer sections.

Resin Film Infusion and Resin Transfer Moulding techniques were evaluated for the liquid moulding.

Phase 2 covered the design and manufacture of all the outboard, or type 3, stringers for the DASA full scale wing test. This involved use of the most cost effective preform scenario, deduced from earlier studies, and the use of integrally heated RTM tooling.

The prime deliverables of the program were:-

A validated stringer design methodology compatible with the DASA wing

A validated production methodology for cost effective stringer manufacture

Manufacture of Demonstration and Full Scale Test stringers as agreed between DASA and CRC-ACS

DASA Assembly Method

The assembly method DASA proposed for the wing consists of using pre-cured stringers which are co-bonded to the prepreg wing skin during the cure of the skin itself.

This method enables simple tooling to be used for the final skin cure inclusive of stringers thus, if the stringers can be produced in a cost effective manner, assembly costs will be minimised compared to the co-curing of an integrally stiffened skin.

General Philosophy

The stringer design philosophy was heavily influenced by manufacturing technique and cost. The main structural concern was to match the strength and stiffness of the DASA prepreg stiffeners. *Figure 1* illustrates the wing FEM.

Figure 1. Wing FE Model

Coupon tests were undertaken to verify the 'lamina' strength and stiffness for use in calculations and sub-element coupons taken from the stringer to confirm structural adequacy.

A MS Excel program was developed to undertake analysis of the stringer geometric variables and this was used in conjunction with program GENLAM for generation of the requisite properties to match the DASA wing.

In addition to the technical evaluation of the stringers - compatible to the composite wing requirements - a costing exercise was undertaken. Further to material costs this evaluated various manufacturing procedures such as hand lay-up, drape forming, RTM and RFI, as appropriate to the material.

PHASE 1

Stringer Design

The deliverables to DASA for Phase 1 of the program were 3 stringers of 2 metres length for incorporation in to a large compression test panel in Germany. The stringers had to match or better the current DASA designed stringers manufactured by conventional prepreg technology.

All intermediate wing stringers (Type 2) consisted of flanges and additional core in the blade zone. Designs with no core tended to be overweight. Note also the requirement for a layer of glass fibre on the insides of the stringer for lightning strike purposes and Airtech Release Ply G on the bond surface of the flange.

Calculations were also undertaken on the stability of the blade and flange in comparison to the baseline DASA design. Damage Tolerance requirements stipulated the stringers must be capable of withstanding complete disbond from the wing between adjacent rib stations.

Properties for the stringer stiffness were obtained from lamina testing. In general stiffness properties of the fabric/RTM6 combinations compared favourably with the theoretically values given by DASA for the prepreg .

Following manufacture of the representative stringer lengths several sub-element coupons were cut from the blade and flange and tested. Prime among these tests was the compressive stringer section test where the required load at Room Temperature was specified by DASA as 295KN: see *Figure2*.

Figure 2. Compression T piece from Stringer

Stringer Manufacture

Each cure produced two stringers from an I-Beam geometry, the final stringer dimensions being obtained by trimming following cure: see *Figure 3* which shows the mandrels in the full assembly tool.

Figure 3: Mandrels in RTM tool.

The stringer manufacture can be defined as being in two stages:
Preform Manufacture
Resin Injection and Cure (RTM or RFI)

Preform Manufacture

For Phase 1 the preform was produced by drape forming the channel sections prior to assembly in the tool. The core preform was designed to fill the interstitial void during resin impregnation at a 60% fibre volume fraction. Of particular criticality are:-

- Peel Ply incorporation
- Mould preparation
- Insertion of mandrels in the tool
- Alignment of the preforms
- Incorporation of the Rohacell thermal expansion 'valves'

Resin Injection and Cure

Two methods of resin infiltration in to the preform were evaluated: Resin Film Infusion (RFI) and Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM).

RFI methods were trialed on a tool of one metre length. The RFI process produced reasonable beams but it was decided, owing to timescale restraints, to use the more familiar RTM process to produce the test panel stringers.

During the limited RFI trials undertaken during Phase 1 many lessons were learnt, in particular on the avoidance of dry spots and surface porosity, incorporation of the peel ply, the effectiveness of the end dams, cure cycle dwell times, and use of RTM6 in both the liquid and B-staged state.

Resin Transfer Moulding was the method eventually chosen to produce the stringers for Phase 1 and can be illustrated by *Figure 4*.

Figure 4: RTM Set Up

Stringer Machining

Two stringers were produced from each I-beam. For flange trimming a hand-held cutter was used with a steel rule guide clamped in position to locate the edge of the flange. A diamond tipped blade was then used to separate the I-beam into two stringers, this initial cut being half way up the web. Final cuts were then made for the stringer flange width using a preform mandrel and Hand Router. The web was machined to the correct height by using a milling head loaded with a small diamond tipped blade. This procedure was unwieldy and not a production friendly scenario. During Phase 2 a more automatic procedure was developed using a specifically designed machining jig on a rail system.

Quality

The compression panel stringers were delivered to DASA on schedule on July 3 1996. Dimensional control of the components was good and subsequent photomicrographs illustrated very low porosity.

Coupon Testing

Lamina tension and compression tests were devised to investigate the basic material properties for the materials used in Phase 1. Tests were undertaken in the 0°, 45° and 90° directions to evaluate the prime lamina properties. Tension tests were used to determine both the tensile and shear properties for each of the materials tested.

DASA Sub-Element Testing

It was a requirement of the project to undertake sub-element testing on components taken directly from representative manufactured stringers. The testing consisted of plain and holed compression specimens, open hole tension and bearing test coupons cut from both the stringer flange and blade.

Characteristic full stringer T-sections with holes were also tested in compression. *Figure 5* summarises typical test results.

Specimen Type	Material	Conditioning	Test Temp. °C	Ult. Failure (kN)	Ult. Stress (MPa)	Ult. Strain (µε)
T	stringer	none	RT	310.9	396	5167
A	flange	none	RT	51.9	756	9783
C - 4mm hole	flange	none	RT	60.9	516	6687
C - 6mm hole	flange	none	RT	55.8	506	6557
C - 8mm hole	flange	none	RT	54.6	496	6432
C - 6mm hole	flange	70°C/H ₂ O	70°C	42.8	393	5052
D	flange	none	RT	103.5	872	8999
D	flange	70°C/H ₂ O	70°C			
B	flange	none	RT	186.8	911.7	2096
A	web	none	RT	200.2	703	9231
C - 4mm hole	web	none	RT	225.1	492	6457
C - 8mm hole	web	none	RT	210.1	455	5967
C - 12mm hole	web	none	RT	175.9	369	4847
C - 8mm hole	web	70°C/H ₂ O	70°C	155.0	336	4420
D	web	none	RT	270.5	810	9459
D	web	70°C/H ₂ O	70°C			
B	web	none	RT	40.0	718.3	1514

Figure 5. Summary of Phase 1 results

In addition interlaminar shears, softening temperature, specific gravity and fibre content specimens were taken from the stringer flange.

Environmental conditions investigated covered conditioning to saturation in 70°C water, and MEK, fuel and Skydrol immersion.

Costing

Several companies were approached for materials suitable as preforms for both the core and the flange of the Type 2 stringer.

Shown in *Figure 6* are the basic relative cost estimates of using prepreg against an RTM solution. Costs include raw material, labour, liquid moulding or draping and curing and trimming.

PREPREG VERSUS RTM COSTS FOR TWO 6 METRE T STRINGERS

Figure 6: Comparison between pre-preg and RTM techniques

PHASE 2

Phase 2 of the research task involved finalisation of material choice based on contemporary costs for quantified volumes and production of all the outboard stringers for the DASA full scale composite wing test in Germany. The longest outboard stringer is 3.015 metres long.

Other than the design configuration of the outboard (type 3) stringers the prime thrust of Phase 2 concentrated on the design and manufacture of a 4 metre RTM integrally heated tool.

Stringer Design

The deliverables to DASA for Phase 2 of the program were 4 upper and 2 lower stringers of similar ply build-up but of different length and cross sectional dimension.

Following the material investigations undertaken in Phase 1 non-crimp materials were chosen for the stringer design. Of note is the fact that the outboard stringers (Type 3) did not have 'core material' between the flanges owing to their less demanding structural requirements, compared to the intermediate wing stringers (Type 2).

Properties of the non-crimp material were evaluated from coupon testing.

The non-crimp material was also used for an intermediate (Type 2) stringer design and effective stringer lengths produced in the Phase 1 two metre tool. DASA sub-element coupons were taken from these sections and tested for comparison to the specimens produced during Phase 1. The only structural specimen taken from the Type 3 stringers (4 metre tool) were compression T-pieces for which the target load, as specified by DASA, was 162KN.

Stringer Manufacture

As for Phase 1 the stringers were produced from I-beams, the final stringer dimensions being obtained by trimming following cure.

For Phase 2 the outboard stringer preforms were produced by a special technique developed in Phase 1.

The major difference for the Phase 2 RTM scenario was the use of an integrally heated tool. This avoided the long heat-up time associated with the oven cure used during Phase 1.

Resin Injection and Curing

The resin injection process (RTM) was similar to that used in Phase 1 and is depicted in *Figure 4*. In this case, however, an oven is not required as the tool was heated by electrical elements.

Dry thermal investigatory runs were undertaken to evaluate the integral heating scenario. Design of the heat control system, incorporating multiple local feedbacks to ensure uniform heating of the tool, was undertaken by personnel from the Mechanical Engineering Department of Monash University.

During the dry run 42 thermocouples were placed in the tool and real time temperature measurements taken for comparison to theoretical calculations.

Following satisfactory dry runs, and the ensuing calibration of the system, the internal thermocouples were removed and control of the tool undertaken by feedback from external thermocouples only.

The Heat Control Unit also incorporated automatic signals for ‘resin injection’, ‘cure complete’ and ‘ready to demold’ operations. *Figure 7* shows a typical part temperature profile during heat-up.

Figure 7. Typical heat up profile

Stringer Machining

As before stringers were produced by machining from the cured I-beams. A special trimming mechanism was designed and manufactured to undertake the final trimming of the stringers.

Quality

All stringers were subjected to quality assessment and controlled by a DASA configured Life Data Sheet. The Life Data Sheet included checks on the Engineering Drawing, Material Data, Fabrication, Inspection and Testing, with the appropriate signatures.

Coupon Testing

Two types of non-crimp material were used during Phase 2 and tests undertaken to evaluate basic material properties. Tests included tension and compression in the longitudinal and transverse directions, shear, and environmental aging effects on compression and shear.

DASA Sub-Element Testing

Sub-element test pieces were taken from the Type 2 stringer section and compared to the results achieved under Phase 1. This testing consisted of plain and holed compression specimens, open hole tension and bearing test coupons cut from both stringer flange and blade. A characteristic full stringer T-section with holes was also tested in compression.

A further sub-element test piece T-section with holes was taken from the Type 3 stringers produced.

Environmental conditioning investigated covered saturation in 70°C water and MEK, fuel, and Skydrol immersion.

Costing

Costing exercises during Phase 2 of the program concentrated on reducing process time with the chosen material and investigating the influence of changing from RTM6 resin to PR500.

Figure 8 illustrates costs for both the intermediary (type 2) and outer (type 3) wing stringers, at an appropriate length, using the standard and non-crimp materials. Use of the non-crimp material gave a saving of 30% over standard fabric scenarios for both the intermediate and outboard stringers. This saving was accrued in both raw material costs and reduction of assembly time.

Figure 8. Cost comparisons standard v. non-crimp

The only other significant cost saving (apart from further material reductions) would be in the automation of the 'moulding operation'. If this could be purely automatic, for example, cost/metre would reduce significantly.

However, incorporation of a stringer twist requirement and thickness variation along the wing spanwise datums may introduce a significant hurdle to the use of a continuous methodology in the manufacture of pre-made stringers.

CONCLUSIONS

Phase 1 of the program culminated in the successful compression testing at DASA of a panel incorporating the stringers to the equivalent of $n=2.3$ wing loading whereupon the test was ceased. No damage of the panel was observed. Equivalent stringer panels produced in conventional prepreg failed at a lower equivalent wing loading.

Investigations during Phase 2 have revealed that the use of non-crimp preform and integral heating with RTM can significantly reduce the cost/metre of the composite stringers.

Analysis of the costing figures indicates that further automation of the preforming and resin injection methods would produce further cost savings.

Following the completion of Phase 2 the future direction of this task is likely to be on a specific aircraft design/development program.

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